

Gaining Competitive Advantage Through Marketing

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Abstract

The very purpose of marketing is to emphasize the uniqueness of the products and services of a concern thus distinct it from that of its competitors. Competitive advantage is an advantage over competitors gained by offering consumers greater value either by means of lower price or by providing greater benefits and service that justifies higher prices. Long term success in business requires building a sustainable competitive advantage despite the entry of new competitors in the market or existing competitors improving their own products or services. Marketing today is one of the most effective strategies that enables organisation to create and sustain competitive advantage. The purpose of this paper is to highlight the importance of marketing and stress on its contribution towards sustaining

Keywords: marketing, effective strategy, competitive advantage.

Introduction

The plain inspiration driving promoting is to include the uniqueness of the things and organizations of an association subsequently remembering it from that of its opponents.

High ground is use over contenders got by offering clients more conspicuous regard either by strategies for cut down expense or by giving more important points of interest and organization that legitimizes higher expenses. Whole deal achievement in business requires building a viable high ground paying little respect to the segment of new adversaries in the market or existing contenders improving their own specific things or organizations. Displaying today is a champion among the best frameworks that engages relationship to make and oversee high ground. The inspiration driving this paper is to include the essentialness of advancing and weight on its responsibility towards supporting

Promoting alludes to the exercises of an organization related with purchasing and offering an item or administration. It incorporates publicizing, offering and conveying items to individuals. Individuals who work in organization’s advertising divisions endeavor to get the consideration of target gatherings of people utilizing trademarks, bundling plan, VIP supports and general media exposure. Marketing involves item improvement, statistical surveying, item dissemination,

deals technique, advertising, and client bolster. Promoting is fundamental in all phases of a business' offering venture

The 4Ps make up a run of the mill advertising blend - Price, Product, Promotion and Place. Value alludes to the esteem that is put for an item. It relies upon expenses of generation, section focused on, capacity of the market to pay, Pricing can likewise be utilized an outline, to separate and improve the picture of a product. Product alludes to the thing really being sold. The item should convey a base level of execution generally even the best work on alternate components of the advertising blend won't do any great. Place refers to the point of offer. In each industry, grabbing the attention of the customer and making it simple for her to get it is the principle point of a decent conveyance or 'place' procedure. Retailers pay a premium for the correct area.

Advancement this alludes to every one of the exercises attempted to make the item or administration known to the client and exchange. This can incorporate promoting, informal, squeeze reports, impetuses, commissions and honors to the exchange. It can likewise incorporate customer plans, coordinate advertising, challenges and prizes.

Upper hand is preference over a contender, which is picked up by offering clients a more prominent incentive than the contender does. Having an edge over a contender results in higher deals and benefits. The business differential or focused edge might be as the accompanying:

1. Product Features and Benefits-uniqueness of a company's product.
2. Location-retail establishments located as per the customers convenience.
3. Staff-well experienced and trained employees.
4. Operating Procedures-smooth running of day to day operation
5. Price-competitive pricing strategies
6. Customer loyalty-consistent customer base.
7. Goodwill-well regarded company in the business company
8. Value-Added Products and/or Services-additional services that complement the original product or service
9. Quality-offering quality products and services

Advertising as an Effective Strategy to Sustain Competitive Advantage

Advertising is the way toward advising the clients about their items and benefits and recognizing it from that of its rivals. Regardless of the how well the organization's items are planned or the best of value conveyed, without suitable advertising techniques, the previously mentioned aggressive edges can't be passed on to the clients. An association may have an upper hand as item includes, value, quality and so forth yet it is just compelling showcasing procedure that will assist the association with making the clients mindful of such highlights. Along these lines, it very well may be said that having a powerful promoting system is additionally essential to manage focused methodology. Viable showcasing systems causes the organization to keep up a predictable client base and furthermore grow it later on.

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Marketing as an Effective Strategy to Sustain Competitive Advantage

Marketing is the process of informing the customers about their products and services and distinguishing it from that of its competitors. Irrespective of the how well the company’s products are designed or the best of quality delivered, without appropriate marketing strategies, the above-mentioned competitive edges cannot be conveyed to the customers. An organisation may have a competitive advantage in the form of product features, price, quality etc but it is only effective marketing strategy that will help the organisation to make the customers aware of such features. Thus, it can be said that having an effective marketing strategy is also vital to sustain competitive strategy. Effective marketing strategies helps the company to maintain a consistent customer base and also expand it in the future.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study is as follows

1. To identify the relevance of marketing of products and services in present scenario.
2. To determine the degree to which the purchasing decisions are influenced by marketing tools employed by companies.
3. To determine the most widely used marketing strategy.
4. To identify the importance of marketing strategies in sustaining competitive advantage.
5. To determine the best marketing strategies for sustaining competitive advantage.
6. To determine the possibilities of a company to gain competitive advantage only through quality goods or competent prices and without any marketing efforts.

Research Methodology

During the study primary source of data collection was adopted by circulating e-questionnaire as an instrument of data collection.

Sample size- the population considered for this study were 25 customers who are regular in purchasing and are influenced by the marketing strategy used by the customers.

Research design: it is a descriptive study designed in the form of a questionnaire to immolate the usefulness of marketing in sustaining competitive advantage.

The main aim of the study is to measure the impact of marketing in today’s world to sustain competitive advantage.

Analysis Table and Interpretation

Is Marketing Helpful in Gaining Competitive Advantage

Source: Excel Output

Inference

This chart depicts the how marketing helps in gaining competitive advantage. 76% of the population feel that marketing contributes in gaining competitive advantage.

The Best Strategy for a Company to Sustain Competitive Advantage on Long Term Basis

Source: Excel Output

Inference

This chart depicts the best strategy that could be adopted by a company to sustain the competitive vantage. 50% of them feel that effective marketing of products will help, 17% of them feel that competitive human resource will help and 33% of the populations feels technological innovation will help in gaining competitive advantage.

Is it Possible for Organisations to Maintain Competitive Advantage Only by Providing Quality Products at Competant Prices without Marketing Efforts

Source: Excel Output

Inference

This chart depicts if the organisation can maintain competitive advantage by providing quality products at competent price without marketing efforts. 42% strongly disagree, 25% agree, 25% is neutral and 8% disagrees that gaining competitive advantage only by providing quality products without any marketing efforts.

Findings

Based on the questionnaire circulated the following were found out:

1. The questionnaire circulated was responded by 25 individuals.
2. 80% of research population agrees that marketing according to them is meant to spread awareness about a product and 20% of the populations agrees that it a promotion of a brand.
3. 91% of the respondents convey that marketing is required in today's economy for promotion of a product and 9% of the respondents convey that it is not required to market today.
4. 58.3% of the respondents agreed that most widely used marketing tool is advertisement and 41.7% say that digital marketing is the most widely used marketing tool today.
5. 66.7% respondents convey that marketing will help in sustaining competitive advantage, whereas 33.3% respondents think marketing may or may not help in sustaining competitive advantage.
6. 33.3% of the respondents feel that marketing helps 90% to gain competitive advantage, 25% feels marketing helps 70% in gaining competitive advantage, and 41.7% feels marketing contributes only 50% to gain competitive advantage.
7. 50% of the respondents feel that effective marketing is the best strategy for gaining competitive advantage on long term basis, 33.3% respondents feel technological innovations is the best strategy, and 16.7% respondents feel competent human resource will help in sustaining competitive advantage.
8. 41.7% respondents strongly disagree that providing quality products with competent price will help in gaining competitive advantage, 25% of are neutral and 25% of the respondents agree that providing quality products with competent price will help in gaining competitive advantage, and 8.3% respondents disagree with the statement.
9. 83.3% respondents convey that their purchasing decisions are influenced by the marketing strategies of the companies and the 8.3% of the respondents convey that they are sometimes or never influenced with the marketing strategies.
10. 66.7% of the respondents feel marketing is a effective tool to gain competitive advantage and 33.3% of the respondents feel that marketing may help in gaining competitive advantage.

Suggestions

- The company's ability to continually develop new and interesting products, while maintaining a strong customer base.
- A product that is better than the competition, with a compelling and obvious reason to purchase. Thus, appropriate marketing tools have to be used to make the product known to the customers.
- Marketing must not only involve advertisements but come up with various ideas such as Google ad words or attractive pop-ups which will define about their products in a short span.
- Have a well built marketing team who will be able get the best ideas to market the products in such a way that they can attract their customers.
- Define the customers, target and prioritise their target customers and get marketing ideas which will draw their attention easily.
- Have a constant watch on the competitors marketing strategies and product innovations which will give better ideas to the companies to improvise in their strategy.
- Continuous innovation in the products will help the companies to stay in the market for a very long time.
- Encourage combo's, offers and exciting packages which will urge the customers to choose their products.

- Keep the brand and quality in mind while framing marketing strategies to promote that as well.
- Market their products with available resources and get the best ways out to reach the maximum customers in short span of time.

Conclusion

Marketing plays a very vital role in every organisation in promotion of product. It not only helps in making the products known to the customers but also promotes the brand and company to the world. Marketing speaks about products and shows how different it is from the others products. It is successful with effective marketing team. By accurately identifying and analyzing firm's target market and its relative competition, the company may recognize potential opportunities for success in selling the product or service. These opportunities, which the competitors may have overlooked, will provide firm with the vision to develop marketing mixes far superior than the competitors. To ensure firm's market staying power and survival in today's marketplace, it is important to gain and maintain a competitive differential advantage in the target market. Looking for continuous innovations and building a better marketing team on everyday basis will help the companies gaining competitive advantage.

There are immense chances where marketing will turn out to be an important tool to implement in the organisation to make them competitive and remain in the market for a longer period of time. The future of market has wide scope and will help the companies to gain advantage in the market.

The organization should equip itself for the changes made in the corporate system and identify ways to make its step forward and gain advantage over the market.

